

D2.5 First version of the project Data Viewer

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Executive Summary

This deliverable contains a description of the website known as “EERIE Data Viewer”. It summarizes the main contents and features of its interactive sections. This is the first version of the Viewer, which is to be completed towards the end of the project when the full EERIE simulation results are available. It is available at <https://dev.eerie.predictia.es>. It is important to note that this environment is not stable – it is a development instance. This report is structured as follows: Section 1 contains the introduction, section 2 summarizes the contents of the Home (the landing page), section 3 explains the Atlas, section 4 the Storylines, section 5 the Science art section, and in section 6 the future additions planned are explained.

1. Introduction

In EERIE there is a great interest in novel data visualization techniques and on making the project results more accessible both to the scientific community and to the general public. That is why the development of a Data Viewer was planned as part of the project. The contents of the Viewer were planned to be based upon previous experiences such as the PRIMAVERA User Interface Platform and the IPCC AR6 atlas. The first version of the Viewer is the milestone #6 and is to be described in the present deliverable, while the last, definitive version, is scheduled for the end of the project (M46). During the first months of EERIE, feedback was gathered from the partners on how the contents of EERIE Data Viewer would look, a process that continues now as the first version has become available internally. It is important to note that the current version of the Viewer is not public and is being distributed only internally in the project. The Viewer is planned to be published when the products from the simulations of the phase 1 are available.

2. Home

Figure 1 shows the landing page for the Viewer as of May 29, 2025. The Earth is shown with animated streamlines representing the sea surface velocity for January 1, 1970 in the ICON historical run. This field showcases how the eddies are resolved, which is the core goal of the EERIE project.

Figure 1: EERIE Data Viewer landing page. The field shown are the streamlines for the sea surface velocity for January 1, 1970 in the ICON historical run

When hovering over the icons at the left-hand side, they expand to the links to the main sub-pages: HOME, ATLAS, STORYLINES and SCIENCE ART. These subpages are described in the following sections. At the right, the user can choose between three showcases: Eddy-rich, High resolution and Experiment coordination. At the present only the Eddy-rich is implemented, which is the one selected by default. This showcase is focused on demonstrating how EERIE models resolve the eddies. The high resolution will showcase the fine details resolved by EERIE models, compared with lower resolution simulations. While the experiment coordination will showcase that the EERIE simulations are the first eddy resolving centennial simulations, reaching the year 2050.

3. Atlas

3.1. Main features

The Atlas enables two main dimensions of data analysis: a spatial analysis through maps and a temporal analysis through time series on predefined regions. As in other viewers with similar purposes such as the [IPCC AR6 WGI Interactive Atlas](#) or the [Copernicus Interactive Climate Atlas](#), maps constitute the main graphical element and serve to provide access to the temporal analysis.

Maps are presented over an Earth's globe in the form of a raster layer, also known as heatmap, with a horizontal resolution of 0.25 degrees (figure 2). This is the common grid that is being used in the project. Note that the original model grids reach a significantly higher resolution but, because of data availability limitations, the current version of the Viewer uses 0.25. A resolution increase will be considered in the future.

The layer to be displayed is chosen by the user in a set of dropdown menus. It is also possible to display time series by choosing a region over the map.

Figure 2: The atlas main view, displaying the surface air temperature for the Icon model.

While heat maps are used in general, the wind field is an exception, as it is shown as coloured, animated streamlines (figure 3). This kind of visualization has proven to be very popular on the internet and will be one of the highlights of the Viewer.

Figure 3: Screenshot showing the streamlines visualization used for the wind.

Another important feature in the Viewer are the dynamic color maps. In this kind of visualization, is it usually not possible to find color maps with enough contrast to make all relevant patterns distinguishable but also perceptually uniform enough. The solution is to allow the user to customize the bounds of the color map at will (figure 4).

Figure 4: Options allowing the user to customize the color map and colorbar used, including the range, opacity, overlay and different colormaps to choose from.

While the spherical Earth view is very attractive, in many cases it is more practical to be able to see the whole Earth surface at a glance. This is why the Viewer users have a “basemap” option that allows them to change the map to an equirectangular projection or an Robinson projection (figure 5). When selected, the transition happens smoothly with a nice animation.

Figure 5: Screenshot showing the map in Robinson projection.

The menus at the right side of the screen allow the user to choose the field to visualize. We call these the analysis dimensions. The following dimensions are available:

- Dataset: The set of data to visualize, which can be observations or EERIE model datasets. The EERIE experiments are grouped under the labels control, historical, historical AMIP. Some of these will include different experiments together that make sense to merge for analysis. For example control 1950 and control 1850. In the future, “historical” will be replaced by the future ssp scenarios that will still include the historical climatologies showing the centennial evolution of the simulated climate from 1950 (1850) to 2050.
- Member: The Earth-system model used and, in some cases (like AMIP ensembles), its configuration.
- Variable: Variable to be shown. Options right now include:
 - Near-Surface Wind Speed
 - Daily Maximum Near-Surface Air Temperature,
 - Daily Minimum Near-Surface Air Temperature
 - Sea Surface Temperature
 - Total Cloud Cover Percentage
 - Eddy Kinetic Energy: This variable is computed from the sea level using the geostrophic equations. Because of this, it is not available near the equator.
 - Precipitation
 - Sea Surface Height Above Geoid

- Quantity: Different available quantities for this product (for example raw value and anomaly).
- Period: Period used to compute the climatology or the trend, for example 1951-1980.
- Time filter: Can be used to select the whole year or one of the climatological seasons.
- Region set: Available for time series. It allows the user to choose the region set to display on the map. Currently two region sets are available, the IPCC AR6 WGI regions and the Eddy regions, which are ocean regions defined in EERIE for their special interest.

All this information is available to the frontend as zarr datasets (Moore, J. A. (2023)).

3.2. Underlying data and code

The underlying zarr files that are read by the Viewer are computed by a set of python scripts. The source code is available in Github¹ and can be used to reproduce the results, thus following the FAIR principles. The zarr files are published in an intake catalogue hosted by DKRZ².

The following is a schematic description of the main workflow:

- Open the intake catalogue (can be “cloud” or “levante”).
- Loop over the variables.
- Open the entry in the catalogue as an xarray dataset.
- Rename the variable if needed together with coordinates.
- Loop over the analysis dimensions (time_filter, period). For each of them compute the product, regrid to a common grid using conservative regridding, add the analysis dimensions as dimensions to the xarray dataset and append it to a list.
- Merge all the products into a single dataset and save it to netCDF using dask.
- A separate script converts the netCDFs to zarr and uploads it to the storage, defining the chunks so there is a single chunk for each map or time series.

There are more scripts for downloading and preparing the observations, computing the Eddy Kinetic Energy etc.

¹ <https://github.com/eerie-project/eerie-viewer-workflows>

² https://github.com/eerie-project/intake_catalogues

3.3. Technical implementation

This section describes the technical aspects of the current Data Viewer implementation, which is mainly based on the use of the [Zarr](#) data format and [WebGL](#). Using Zarr and WebGL to represent geospatial data constitutes a significant evolution in the architecture of data delivery and visualization, particularly when compared to traditional OGC [WMS](#) (Open Geospatial Consortium Web Map Service) systems. This approach is especially powerful when dealing with large, multidimensional datasets.

Zarr is designed to handle n-dimensional arrays efficiently. Internally, it chunks datasets along each dimension (e.g., latitude, longitude, time, altitude), storing each chunk as a compressed binary file—usually in a format like Blosc or Zlib. These chunks are stored as individual objects in a hierarchical directory structure, which can be hosted on a local file system or on cloud object stores.

Unlike traditional raster formats (e.g. GeoTIFF, NetCDF) or server-driven tile services (e.g., WMS), Zarr allows clients to selectively request and decompress only the specific chunks they need. For example, if a user is interested in a time slice over a small region, only those chunks intersecting the bounding box and time index are retrieved. This eliminates the need for large file downloads or centralized server-side rendering.

On the other hand, WebGL is a JavaScript API that allows for rendering interactive 2D and 3D graphics using the GPU directly in the browser. WMS, in contrast, typically requires a monolithic server environment with configured layers, rendering styles (e.g. based on [SLDs](#)), and image caching strategies. This creates operational overhead and limits dynamic user-driven exploration of the data. Moreover, a WMS-based approach can be computationally expensive and introduce server-side latency mostly when working with high resolution datasets.

The Zarr + WebGL paradigm encourages a stateless architecture. Since Zarr is just a set of static files and WebGL runs entirely on the client, this model allows applications to be deployed in fully serverless environments. No GIS server (like GeoServer or MapServer) is needed to manage rendering. Instead, applications serve lightweight JavaScript frontends and point to cloud-hosted datasets. This approach is more resilient, cheaper to scale, and better suited for modern CI/CD pipelines or edge-computing scenarios.

The combination of Zarr and WebGL is inherently more compatible with modern data delivery protocols, especially those conforming to the Cloud Optimized Geospatial Ecosystem (e.g., STAC,

COGs, and OPeNDAP-compatible APIs). Because Zarr supports HTTP range requests and partial I/O, it integrates well with web infrastructure and caching strategies like CDNs. This means geospatial clients can interact with petabyte-scale datasets directly from cloud storage with low latency, bypassing the need for dedicated tile servers or heavy middleware layers.

The combination of Zarr and WebGL enable the following features:

- GPU-based slicing and real-time animation through shaders.
- Dynamic color mapping and opacity transfer functions without server re-rendering.
- Multiscale rendering by using precomputed Zarr pyramids or multi-resolution levels.
- Visualization based on choropleths but also using animations

The current implementation makes use of the following libraries and tools:

- [React](#) (version 19.0.0) has been used as the main TypeScript framework. React is a free and open-source front-end JavaScript library which aims to make building user interfaces based on components.
- [Zarrita.js](#) (version 0.5.1) is a collection of JavaScript modules which exports independent functions to interact with Zarr entities (e.g. stores, arrays, and groups). Zarrita is used to retrieve and decompress Zarr objects.
- [Three.js](#) (version 0.173.0) is a cross-browser JavaScript library and application programming interface (API) used to create computer graphics in a web browser using WebGL. [Three.js](#) is used by the Three-globe library to ease the use of WebGL.
- [Three-globe](#) (version 2.41.12) is a ThreeJS WebGL class to represent data visualization layers on a globe, using a spherical projection.
- [VisX](#) (version 3.12.0) is a collection of reusable low-level visualization components which is used for rendering charts (e.g. time series plots).
- [Turf.js](#) (version 7.2.0) is a JavaScript library for spatial analysis which include traditional spatial operations, helper functions for creating and modifying GeoJSON files. Turf.js is used to work with the GeoJSON-based definition of regions. For instance, Turf.js resolves if a click on the map/globe resides inside a specific polygon (e.g. an IPCC region).
- [Zustand](#) (version 5.0.2) is a small, fast, and scalable state management solution.
- [Tailwind CSS](#) (version 4.0.8) is an open-source CSS framework.

4. Storylines

The Storyline section contains (figure 6) interactive storymaps after the storylines developed by EERIE. By the time this deliverable was submitted, the Disease Outbreaks in South America storyline was included in this first version. At least three more storylines will be added by the end of the project.

A storymap is an interactive tool that combines maps with narrative content. As you scroll through the story, text, images, and multimedia appear alongside a map that updates to show relevant locations or data. The Atlas content itself is leveraged to illustrate the story, together with other data and multimedia content provided by the storyline authors. The storymaps are co-designed with these authors, by filling a template where the storymap layout is described in detail.

Figure 6: Screenshot of the storylines section, showing the beginning of the “Climate drivers of infectious disease outbreaks in South America” story.

5. Science art

The Science Art section is used to display the science art videos produced with EERIE data (also from previous or sibling projects). As of the moment of document submission there are three videos available: “Eyes on the sea ice”, “A tail wind tale” and “An Eddy-rich story” (figure 7).

Figure 7: Screenshot of the science art section.

6. Future work

In the landing page, the showcases ‘High resolution’ and ‘Experiment coordination’ will be completed with visualizations. In the case of ‘High resolution’, this will include higher resolution maps up to 0.125 degrees to show all the spatial detail that the EERIE models are able to resolve.

In the Atlas, the available products are soon to be extended with the missing phase 1 simulations that are scheduled to be available by September 2025. The main datasets to be included are the HadGEM and IFS-NEMO models, and the future scenario runs. Further in the project, the phase2 simulations will be included too. Also, the inclusion of new variables and/or derived indices is actively considered, especially important ocean variables such as salinity, and also other products such as warming stripes or annual cycles. Depending on data availability, new graphical products (e.g. to analyze the temporal dimension over specific regions in different ways) will be designed and implemented.

In the Storylines section, at least three more storylines will be added by the end of the project.

In the Science Art section, more videos will be added. For example a video entitled “Life of an Eddy” is planned and the data has been already prepared.

Acronyms

IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

WCRP – World Climate Research Programme

CMIP – Coupled Model Intercomparison Project

GMD – Geoscientific Model Development journal

HighResMIP – High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project

CMIP7 FastTrack (CMIP7 AFT)

References

- Kacper Nowak. (2024). FESOM/implicit_filter: Implements first-party support for NEMO Orca grids as well as longitude-latitude grids. (Latest). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14285151>
- Moore, J. A. (2023). [CORDI 2023] Zarr: A Cloud-Optimized Storage for Interactive Access of Large Arrays. 1st Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI), Karlsruhe, Germany. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8340248>
- Roberts, M. J., Jung, T., Ortega, P., Ghosh, R., Wachsmann, F., von Storch, J.-S., Kroeger, J., Aengenheyster, M., & Roberts, C. (2024). Phase 1 simulations, including HighResMIP and CMIP6-PI-control simulations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14288726>
- Roberts, M. J., Reed, K. A., Bao, Q., Barsugli, J. J., Camargo, S. J., Caron, L.-P., Chang, P., Chen, C.-T., Christensen, H. M., Danabasoglu, G., Frenger, I., Fučkar, N. S., ul Hasson, S., Hewitt, H. T., Huang, H., Kim, D., Kodama, C., Lai, M., Leung, L.-Y. R., Mizuta, R., Nobre, P., Ortega, P., Paquin, D., Roberts, C. D., Scoccimarro, E., Seddon, J., Treguier, A. M., Tu, C.-Y., Ullrich, P. A., Vidale, P. L., Wehner, M. F., Zarzycki, C. M., Zhang, B., Zhang, W., and Zhao, M.: High-Resolution Model Intercomparison Project phase 2 (HighResMIP2) towards CMIP7, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 18, 1307–1332, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-18-1307-2025>, 2025.
- SCImago, (n.d.). SJR — SCImago Journal & Country Rank [Portal]. Retrieved 2025-04-23, from <http://www.scimagojr.com>

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